

The Life Circles of Kani Tribes in Tirunelveli District, Tamil Nadu

M. Selvaraju,

Ph.D. Scholar,

Thiruvalluvar Government Arts College,
Rasipuram, Namakkal - 637401.

Dr. P. Prakash

Associate Professor of History,

Thiruvalluvar Government Arts College,
Rasipuram, Namakkal - 637401.

ABSTRACT

The Kanis or Kanikkarn are the tribal living amidst mountain fastnesses religious tribal people of Tirunelveli district and in Kanyakumari district, which lie on either side of the Western Ghats. According to 2011 census there are 24,000 Kankkar living in several district of Kerala and Tamilnadu. The land of the people living area around will be Gardens, trees, forest included delicious. The modern by development they are life charge although seen in the forest in animals and Nature with Biology continuously strick to it coming Amazing thing. The Kani festival period games for Jumping and Thumpi, Jumping included land people will performs traditional folk dances. The annually land of the people Harvest Thirunal “Onam” that of in the name is celebration. The rain not raining in times special ritual conduct, the right ran, “Odavelli” in contexts that cutout from that water are mountain nature resources greatly are using their medical knowledge. The Kani tribal people very important religious followed by traditional system.

Key words: Kani tribals, Western Ghats, Rituals, Onam, Odavelli.

Introduction

The Kanis or Kanikkars are the tribe living amidst the mountain fastnesses of Ambasamudram taluk of Tirunelveli district and in Kanyakumari district, which lie on either side of the Western Ghats. The Kanis are known by several synonyms such as Kaniyan, Kanikkar, Kanikarans, Velanmars and Malainrasans. They are also known as mountains.

Kanikkaran are a tribal community found in the Southern parts of Kerala and Tamil Nadu states in India. According to 2011 census there are 24,000 Kanikkars, living in several districts of Kerala and Tamil Nadu. They well in forests or near to forests in Thiruvananthapuram and Kollam in Kerala and Kanyakumari and Tirunelveli districts.

Through they cultivate everything and make agricultural and religion ritual the main profession and land tribal people will meet religion community for the forest areas in documentary one to taluk want that liked for that opportunity Tirunelveli district.

Kani Tribals:

The tribels found in the study area is known as Kanikaran or Kani. They are traditionally as nomadic community. Kanikaran tribes speak Tamil and Malayalam as their language. They are short in nature, usually dark skinned and carry a self-sustaining existences based on farming. Earlier they lived under rock shades and caves, which provided shelter to these people. Then habits and manners have undergone change to outside contacts. Every tribal group has a tribal chief. They are today living in several tribal hamblets, each consisting of 5-20 familiar disbursed in a around the forest areas of Tirunelveli hills in Tirunelveli district.

As per the 1981 census of Tirunelveli district, the Kanikkaran population is 0.33% of the total population, tribal population 3,65,932 of the district. As per the 2011 census of Tirunelveli district of Tamil Nadu has total population 3,07,233 of the district, the Kanikkaran population is 49.4% of the total population.

The Kanikkaran of Mundamthurai Sanctuary seem to be the migrants from Thiruvanthapuram of Kerala State and they may have entered in to Tamil Nadu. Most of the Kani tribals have a general knowledge of medicinal plants that are used for Kani tribals Religions Natural People in Tirunelveli district. The Kani's still supplement their food by gathering roots and tubers from the nearby forest cares. They are social and economically backward and most of the are very

poor. They are also engaged in seasonal collection of honey. They cultivate edible plants, like tapioca, banana, millets, and cash crops, such as pepper, coconut, aeronaut and cashewnut.

The Religions of Kani tribes:

The Kanis or Kanikkaras are the tribes living amidst the mountain fastnesses of Ambasamudram taluk of Tirunelveli district and Kanyakumari district, which lie on either side of the Western Ghats. The Religions each Kani settlement has got a headman called Muttukani. He is assisted by Vizhi Kani, whose duty is to compel the presence of any Kani in the Caste Panchayat on the orders of the Muttukani. The functions of a Vizhi kani are similar to those of a Thalayarl in non-tribal villages. The society of the Kani people very different.

Nature Suitable Life

The Kani Tribes people name of document picture has been takethem. Once upon a time as nomads lived land tribal people, now west contivity of the mountains south in area permanently setting down living are coming theirs food required throughout there forest areas the results depends. There is land of the people house soil, stones, forest, grass, coconut and with are setup. Theirs special construction lony period working horses provided.

Land of the People Strength:

Land people living are around will be gardens, trees, forest included delicious Biology all the area giving in this featured scenes one mesmerizing in terms of wonderfully are filmed us their for habit itself pick up go to are leaving. These people are 150 feet tall in trees to climbing ability. Those we received honey to take tree left tree left tree jump to the extent power creators. Modern by development they are life little by little change Although seen in the forest in animals and nature with Biology continuously stick it coming Amazing thing.

Kani Festivals and Rituals:

The Annually land of the people Harvest Thirnal “Onam” that of in the name of celebrated they are will workship senior Goddess Karumendiy Amman. This which Onam on the feast day in one place get together they worship. Women traditional clothing wearing dance in song will be involved.

Kani Festival period Games:

Kani Tribes people of Festival period Games for Thumpi Jumping, Jumping Jumping, included land people will performs Traditional Folk Danles, Rope... dragging, slipping tree, climbing such as game competitions are conducted “Karthikai give” that of festival land people celebrating another famous received festival is mostly ancestors that’s it land people worshiped are coming.

Marriage Practice:

He is the land that speaks languages is in Tamil Unique case language is their administrative in the system jointed land that of Village Chairman, visited that of Administrator, Elder that of Agriculture Expert, Pilate that of Doctor those, there are land of the people in life important event. This people marriage event, specific on the day adults get together conclusion are doing many for couples just marriages here often are conducted by the leaves became evening as that are building. They are of custom according to married next 7 days together to live should not it.

Kani People Final Ritual:

The rain not raining in times, special Ritual conduct, the Right rain “Odavelli” in contexts that of flags cut out from that water are sipping all medical for treatments, Green tea, decoction, herb powder, herb composition as west continuing of the mountain nature, resources greatly are using their medical knowledgeable a in generation from another to generation very much with concern is taught.

Honey Collecting:

The Kani tribal people nature the way Agricultural followed by living are coming food products, medical herbs to the outside world sold to earn have started honey collection theirs seasonal it is a profession basket, braiding bamboo craft materials by hand will do flower sewing included in industries too are involved. Natural food items towards world people obic have in position, land of the people Agriculture Abundant, importance has caused.

Learn Choose Land people:

The chemical without undertake land of the people 2021, for agriculture organic quality proof in provided. This for the, people, Government School acting is coming here after reading next

day door to towns to up for study are going well done will read land people, police department, forest department, teachers etc., in companies working to the extent have risen west continuity on the mountain living a Land Tribes Nature to us provided by boon them.

CONCLUSION:

This study revealed that the religious land people of life strength. The right of the collection could have been given to the Kani purpose society which was willing to have the lease. Such a step will be extremely helpful to the Kanis. The Kani Tribals People only for Kani festival and Rituals, period of Games and Marriage Practice. The Kanikkar importance work for Honey Collecting and nature the way agriculture followed by living are food products, medical herbs, and medicinal plants. they are society and economically backward most of the are very poor. The Kani people religion and culture documentation tribals residing in the deep forest areas are still development on religious. But the mountain living in land tribes nature to us provided by boon them. The chemical without undertake land people 2021, for agriculture organic quality proof in provided at Tirunelveli district.

References:

1. Bakshi, S.C., Pal, A Lexicon of Medicinal plants in India, Nayo Prokash, Calcutta, 1999.
2. Nadkani, India Medical Medica, Popular Prakasam, Bombay, 1976.
3. Magesbabu, N. and Jayaram the Samayam, Tamil Nadu, 2022.
4. Sharma P.P. Traditional knowledge on plant in India, 2003.
5. Viswanathan, M.B, Ethnobotay of the Malayalis in North Arcot district, Tamil Nadu, India. 1977.
6. Chatterjee A. The Tribals people in India, 1999.
7. Gamble J.S. The Flora of the Presidency of Madras, 1975.
8. Haris. M. The rice of Anthropological theory History of Theories of Culture, London, 1947.
9. Rangachari. K, Castes and Tribes of South India, Vol-I, 1986.

10. Vijayan, A traditional Remedies of Kani Tribes of Kottar Reserve Forest, Kerala. 1987.
11. Kanikkaran Tribes in India, The Ethnologue website - 21, 2009.
12. Venkataragan. L.B., Survey of the Tribes in Kalrayan Hills of South Cences of India, Vol.IX, Part B, 1961.